

Characterizing Voltage Transformers up to 150 kHz: A New Approach to Generate MV Distorted Test Waveforms

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Abstract—The increase in disturbances at frequencies higher than 10 kHz in Medium Voltage (MV) grids has led to new needs related to the characterization of Instrument Transformers (ITs) involved in the monitoring of these disturbances. In this context, this paper presents a novel generation and measurement setup for the characterization of MV Voltage Transformers (VTs) up to 150 kHz. The proposed approach is based on the generation of test signals composed of a tone at MV and power frequency and one at reduced amplitude and higher frequency. By implementing a suitable compensation technique, the traceability of the two tones is ensured before their combination.

Index Terms—Instrument Transformers, Power Quality, high-frequency harmonics, metrological traceability.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing frequency of power converters and their integration into hybrid Medium Voltage (MV) AC and DC grids are making the monitoring of High Frequency (HF) distortion a crucial task. The measurement chain for monitoring such harmonics must include Instrument Transformers (ITs), thus, their frequency performance significantly impacts the overall measurement accuracy. In this context, the recently released IEC 61869-1 Ed 2 [1] introduces extensions to the accuracy classes of ITs in frequency; however, it lacks guidance on assessing accuracy at frequencies other than the power frequency. The European research project ADMIT [2] has been funded to address this gap by developing the metrological framework for the traceable characterization of MV IT up to 150 kHz. Considering the scientific literature facing this issue, the setups presented in [3], [4] for the characterization of Voltage Transformers (VT, both inductive as well as Low Power Voltage Transformers, LPVTs) for MV applications up to 150 kHz are designed to generate a signal composed of a fundamental tone at the MV level and a superimposed HF distortion at reduced amplitude. The power frequency component is generated using a step-up transformer, whereas the spectral tones are superimposed through the series connection of a wideband Low Voltage (LV) generator. This solution involves using a capacitor in parallel with the step-up transformer to mitigate the HF voltage drop across the step-up high voltage terminals, but it presents drawbacks with increasing primary voltage due to current demand and capacitor sizing/cost. This paper introduces a novel generation and measurement setup for VTs characterization at MV up to 150 kHz. Unlike previous solutions [3], [4], it does not include the capacitor. Instead, it achieves a strong reduction in HF voltage drop on the step-up transformer by compensating it

through a suitable HF voltage applied at the low voltage side of the step-up transformer. By eliminating the drop on the step-up transformer, it's possible to consider the two sources separately, thus providing metrological traceability on the two tones (MV power frequency and HF LV) separately, before their combination.

II. THE PROPOSED APPROACH

Figure 1 provides the circuitual representation of the proposed calibration setup. The step-up transformer is electrically modelled by an ideal transformer with a series impedance Z_{su} ; the HF generator is approximated by an ideal voltage generator. The two generators are connected in series to the Device Under Test (DUT) represented by an impedance (Z_{DUT}). Assuming a linear behaviour of the step-up transformer for the HF signal, the superposition of the effects can be applied. By switching on only the HF generator, the voltage drop across Z_{su} is obtained by:

$$\overline{\Delta V} = \overline{V_{HF}} \frac{Z_{su}}{Z_{DUT} + Z_{su}} \quad (1)$$

This voltage drop introduces a systematic error in the determination of the HF voltage applied to the DUT. A way to compensate for this error is to generate a HF voltage, with a suitable phase angle, with the step-up transformer. By the principle of superposition of effects, it is easy to demonstrate that the HF voltage drop is theoretically compensated by applying with the step-up transformer a voltage $\overline{V_{hf}^*}$ at HF equal to:

$$\overline{V_{hf}^*} = |G| \cdot \frac{|Z_{su}|}{|Z_{DUT}|} \cdot e^{j(\varphi_G + \varphi_{su} - \varphi_{DUT})} \quad (2)$$

where G and φ_G are the gain and phase displacement of the step-up transformer, φ_{su} and φ_{DUT} are the phase angles of the step-up output impedance and the DUT. This approach guarantees that the HF voltage applied to the DUT is the quantity $\overline{V_{HF}}$ measured in a traceable way.

III. CALIBRATION SETUP

The initial arrangement of the calibration setup has been performed. An inductive VT with a ratio of 200 V/V (20 kV/100 V) has been employed as a step-up; it is supplied by the chain constituted by a National Instrument generation card and the NF amplifier (150 V, 2 A) with a DC to 500 kHz bandwidth. The HF voltage is provided by a Fluke calibrator.

Fig. 1. Electric scheme of the proposed calibration setup

Fig. 2. Frequency behaviour of the step-up output impedance

Finally, the DUT is a $R - C$ voltage divider with a DC to 1 MHz bandwidth designed for MV applications. Its high voltage arm impedance is approximated by a resistance of $100\text{ M}\Omega$ and an overall capacitance of 8 pF . Three voltages are acquired by a suitable acquisition system: the voltage applied to the step-up, the voltage imposed by the calibrator and the voltage at the output of the DUT.

A. Impedance Z_{su}

The impedance at the high voltage side of the step-up Z_{su} is measured by a wide bandwidth impedance analyzer. The interest bandwidth is between 10 kHz and 150 kHz. It is obtained by connecting the analyzer between the high-voltage terminal, short-circuiting the input terminals and connecting them to the terminal "low" of the analyzer. As shown in Fig. 2, impedance Z_{su} has a capacitive behaviour: the phase is close to -90° and the impedance magnitude decreases linearly in a logarithmic-scale graph. The estimated overall capacitance of Z_{su} is $C_{su} = 100\text{ pF}$. Moreover, approximately six resonances are identified.

B. The step-up frequency response

The complex gain G , defined as the ratio between the output step-up transformer over the applied voltage, has been measured by the NI acquisition card, and a Fluke calibrator is

Fig. 3. Magnitude and phase frequency behaviour of the step-up.

used as a voltage source. Its frequency behaviour in the range [10 - 150] kHz is shown in Fig. 2. Several resonances are evident, the maximum gain magnitude, 45 V/V is at 14 kHz. After 50 kHz the magnitude remains lower than 1 V/V with a minimum of 0.3 V/V.

IV. CONCLUSION

A novel setup for characterizing MV IT in the [10-150] kHz range has been introduced. This approach eliminates the need for an HV capacitor parallel to the step-up transformer by compensating the voltage drop through a suitable HF voltage applied at the LV side of the step-up. In this way, the setup ensures separate traceability to power frequency MV and HF LV sinewaves before their combination. Preliminary results of the step-up characterization are presented in this abstract, with planned future work including experimental tests on a commercial LPVT to validate the proposed procedure.

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